

Real and synthetic scenarios generated for the development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems

SYNERGIES

D7.3 SYNERGIES platform release v2

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

D7.3 is a deliverable of type 'demonstrator', materialised as a software prototype — specifically, a web application accessible at <https://app.synergies-ccam.eu/>. This document reports on the second release of the SYNERGIES Platform (v2, M24), describing its new features, the status of platform requirements, and the roadmap towards the final release. Building upon the federated architecture and first platform release documented in D7.2, this iteration delivers six concrete improvements: expansion of the Marketplace to twelve tools covering the full scenario lifecycle; connection of the FAME Test Data Space as a second federated external data source via an IDSA and Gaia-X compliant EDC connector; upload of more than 2,700 consortium-generated scenarios to the SYNERGIES Scenario Database; integration of the SYNERGIES User Handbook v1.0 and eight video tutorials into the platform Documentation section; a redesign of the Query Manager frontend to improve scenario discovery; and resolution of a sign-up failure affecting users in corporate email environments. All five objectives established for this milestone have been met. At the time of submission, the platform counts 62 registered users.

This deliverable, as specified in Annex I, refers to Tasks T7.1, T7.2, and T7.4. Their respective contributions to this release are as follows. T7.1 — Platform Architecture and Design: the federation layer, SCDB connector model, and Marketplace plugin architecture established in T7.1 and reported in D7.1 directly enabled the new integrations delivered in v2 — the FAME TDS connector and the twelve Marketplace tools — without requiring any structural changes, validating the extensibility and modularity of the architecture. T7.2 — Test and Validation of the Scenario Platform System: internal testing by consortium members following the v1 release identified usability deficiencies that directly drove the Query Manager redesign (Section 2.3) and the sign-up process overhaul (Section 2.6); T7.2 activities will continue in preparation for D7.5 (Platform Mitigation Plan, M30). T7.4 — User Handbook and Documentation: the SYNERGIES User Handbook v1.0 has been embedded directly in the platform's Documentation section, providing Introduction, Glossary & Acronyms, and User Manual modules to all users, complemented by eight video tutorials covering the core platform workflows.

From a requirements perspective, 23 of the 61 requirements originally defined in D2.1 are now fully addressed and a further 16 are partly met, a substantial progression from the state reported in D7.2. Particularly significant advances in this release are the full resolution of Req_46 (Detection of Similar Scenarios) through the PROVEN Scenario Extraction tool's ontology-based GraphDB workflow, Req_48 (User Documentation) through the integrated handbook and tutorials, and the simultaneous strengthening of five interoperability and federation requirements through the FAME TDS integration. The remaining open requirements — notably those concerning input data quality (Req_15), scenario filtering by regulation (Req_23), and platform-level reporting and analytics (Req_40) — are scoped for resolution in the final platform release (D7.4, M36), with clear technical dependencies identified. The trajectory towards that final release is well-defined: migration to vendor-agnostic open-source infrastructure, introduction of an advanced ontology-based query engine, and the development of navigable scenario collections will together complete the SYNERGIES platform's ambition to provide a lasting, interoperable, and European-sovereign infrastructure for scenario-based CCAM development and testing.

Keywords: Platform, Scenario Dataspace, Tool Marketplace, CCAM, Virtual testing, Simulation, Scenarios, Datasets, Automated Driving.

2 SYNERGIES PLATFORM – CURRENT STATUS

This section provides a concise reference baseline for the v2 release. A full architectural description, platform access instructions, and visual interface documentation are provided in D7.2 (SYNERGIES Platform Release v1), which remains the primary architectural reference for WP7.

Figure 1 Main page of the SYNERGIES Platform application

2.1 Platform version and access

The SYNERGIES Platform v2 is publicly accessible at:

<https://app.synergies-ccam.eu/>

Registration is open to any user. Account creation requires name, surname, email and a password meeting the platform security criteria. A 6-digit verification code is sent by email to complete registration. For enquiries regarding institutional access, contact the platform team via the Documentation section. At the moment of the submission of this deliverable, the platform had a total number of **62 registered users**.

2.2 Release objectives

The objectives established for Release v2 (M24), as derived from Annex I and internal WP7 planning, were:

1. Expand Marketplace tool offering to at least 10 tools developed by consortium partners.
2. Connect the platform to a second federated external data source beyond SUNRISE databases.
3. Upload at least 1,000 consortium-generated scenarios to the SYNERGIES SCDB.
4. Integrate the SYNERGIES User Handbook v1.0 and video tutorials into the platform Documentation section.
5. Resolve usability issues identified through T7.2 internal testing (sign-up, query manager).

All five objectives have been met in this release, as detailed in Section 3.

3 NEW FEATURES AND ENHANCEMENTS

This release introduces both new platform features and new content registered on the platform. To clarify the distinction:

Platform features refer to new functionalities, architectural changes, or interface redesigns that alter how the platform operates. Content additions refer to new tools, scenarios, or data assets registered on the platform using its existing capabilities.

The developments detailed in this section are organised accordingly:

Platform Features:

- Connection to the FAME Test Data Space as part of the Data Registry (Section 2.2)
- Redesign of the Query Manager frontend interface (Section 2.3)
- New sign-up process and access management (Section 2.6)

Content Additions:

- Addition of new tools to the Marketplace (Section 2.1)
- Upload of project-generated scenarios to the SYNERGIES SCDB (Section 2.4)

Supporting Improvements:

- Platform documentation and video tutorials (Section 2.5)

Collectively, these developments position the SYNERGIES platform as a more mature, accessible, and comprehensive solution for scenario-based CCAM development and testing.

3.1 Addition of New Tools to the Marketplace

The SYNERGIES Marketplace content has been expanded in Release v2 to include a collection of tools developed by project partners. These tools combine both existing solutions and new tools created specifically to fulfil SYNERGIES requirements (as defined in D2.1 section 3.2 Marketplace Requirements). Partner contributions bring expertise in areas such as scenario generation, data conversion, visualization, and analysis, providing a practical toolkit for CCAM scenario-based testing workflows.

The Marketplace interface provides filtering capabilities that help users identify tools matching their requirements. Users can filter by name, execution framework, category, license, input formats, and output formats. The interface also supports switching between card and list views, allowing users to choose their preferred display mode. These features improve the user experience by reducing search time and presenting information in an accessible format (Figure 2).

Figure 2. SYNERGIES Marketplace

Release v2 currently features twelve tools that address different stages of the scenario lifecycle. Category classifications include:

- SSD (Scenario Source Data) Library tools for working with scenario data structures.
- SSD Converter tools for transforming data between formats.
- SSD Analysis tools for extracting insights.
- SSD Generation tools for transforming Raw Data into Scenario Source Data.
- Scenario Generation tools for extracting Scenarios from Scenario Source Data (SSD).
- Data Format tools for foundational data handling.
- Visualization Tools for graphical representation.

The tools support multiple execution frameworks including Python libraries, command-line interfaces (CLI), web applications, and Docker containers, providing flexibility in deployment approaches.

Regarding data interoperability, the tools support a wide range of input formats including SSD, MCAP, OSI Trace, CSV, Parquet, ASAM OpenDRIVE, ASAM OpenLABEL, JPEG, PCD (Point Cloud Data), JSON, simple-scenario format, and motion prediction datasets. Output formats include SSD, MCAP, OSI Trace, ASAM OpenDRIVE, ASAM OpenLABEL, Parquet, DataFrame, JSON, simple-scenario format, and Web UI interfaces. All these formats allow users to construct complete data processing pipelines by chaining multiple tools together, enabling workflows from raw data ingestion through analysis to visualization and reporting. Table 1 below details the current Marketplace offering, with additional tools planned for future releases.

Tool Name	Category	Input	Output	Description
omega-prime-visibility	SSD Library, SSD Analysis	SSD	DataFrame	Computes 2D visibility of moving objects for [omega-prime]
simple-simulation	SSD Converter	simple-scenario	JSON	Execute simulation runs defined by simple-scenario to develop scenario-based testing methods
omega-prime	SSD Library, SSD	MCAP, OSI Trace, SSD, CSV,	MCAP, SSD, OSI Trace, ASAM	Data model/format and python tooling for the scenario source data format

	Converter, Data Format, Visualization Tool	Parquet, ASAM OpenDRIVE	OpenDRIVE, Parquet	
WebLabel Player	WebLABEL, Labelling Tool	Data packages	OpenLabel JSON files	Multi-sensor labeling web application compliant with OpenLabel
betterosi	SSD Library, Data Format, Visualization Tool	MCAP, OSI Trace	MCAP, SSD, OSI Trace	A python library for reading and writing ASAM OSI files using betterproto2
alks-scenarios	Scenario Generation	JSON	simple-scenario	Recreates test scenarios from UN/ECE R.157 E/ECE/TRANS/505/Rev.3/Add.156/Amend.4 Annex 3 pp. 45-56 using simple-scenario
simple-scenario	SSD Generation	JSON	simple-scenario	Quickly generate prototype test scenarios for automated driving
Cuboid Tracking Library (CTL)	3D Dynamic Objects Tracking, Object Tracking	3D Cuboid detections	Cuboid tracks	Python library to add time consistency to cuboid (3D bounding boxes) of objects
omega-prime-trajdata	SSD Converter	Motion Prediction Datasets	SSD	A fork of trajdata using betterproto2 and including a converter to lomega-prime
PROVEN Scenario Extraction	Scenario Identification, Ontology	Openlabel JSON files	RDF files, OpenLabel JSON files with actions and events	This tool accepts as an input ASAM OpenLABEL files (automatically generated from SSD), converts them to RDF format and generates a graphDB following a given ontology. The graphDB is then queried to identify scenarios
omega-to-openlabel	Converter	SSD OmegaPRIME	ASAM OpenLABEL JSON	Python library to convert Omega-Prime files to ASAM OpenLABEL format
Lichtblick-suite	Visualization Tool	OSI trace	Graphical visualization	A visualization tool for mcap traces including OSI Sensor View / Ground Truth

Table 1. Available Tools

3.2 Data Registry: Connection to the FAME Test Data Space

The SYNERGIES platform has added FAME, a project supporting coordination of CCAM testing and evaluation activities across Europe, as part of the Data Registry to enhance data discoverability and management capabilities. FAME's CCAM Test Data Space (TDS) serves as a demonstrator of federated data sharing built on Eclipse Data Space Connector technology, implementing a connector-as-a-service approach that enables secure and standardized data access across the CCAM research community. The integration consisted of the onboarding to the FAME TDS, which involved the deployment of an EDC Data Space Connector. This connector allows discovering Data Assets in an IDSA and Gaia-X compliant data space.

While the current implementation contains a limited number of datasets, this integration represents an important proof-of-concept and a foundational step towards broader interoperability with other CCAM projects following the CCAM Data Sharing Framework 2.0 principles. The registry functionality is seamlessly incorporated into SYNERGIES' existing user interface, allowing researchers to discover and access federated data assets alongside the

platform's native scenario database, thereby paving the way for enhanced cooperation and knowledge exchange within the European CCAM stakeholder community. (Figure 3)

Figure 3. SYNERGIES Dataspace: Data Registry connection to FAME

At the time of this release, the FAME TDS connector exposes 3 data assets discoverable through the SYNERGIES Data Registry interface. A user accessing the Dataspace and navigating to the Data Registry tab can browse these assets, and initiate an access request through the IDSA-compliant data space protocol. Figure 2 shows the registry panel with FAME assets visible alongside SYNERGIES SCDBs. This integration represents the cross-project federated data connection in the SYNERGIES platform and validates the architecture's compliance with CCAM Data Sharing Framework 2.0 principles.

3.3 Query Manager Frontend redesign

The Scenario Dataspace has been redesigned to improve usability and enhance the scenario search workflow. Instead of immediately presenting users with the Query Manager interface, the Dataspace now displays a scenario list as the primary view, provided the user has at least one query defined and stored as a bookmark (Figure 4). When users access the Dataspace, they see results from their most recent query (provided they have at least one query configured for their connected Scenario Databases), giving immediate visibility into available scenarios without requiring manual query execution.

SCDB	NAME	ID	TYPE	ASAM OSC
DEMO-VICOMTECH-25	CutIn_00039	SCEN-8BA26C749062	Concrete	✓
DEMO-VICOMTECH-25	CutIn_00093	SCEN-386F753484A2	Concrete	✓
SYNERGIES	scenario_instance_cut-in_1755867839896918800_0	SCEN-1755867839896918800	Concrete	✓
DEMO-VICOMTECH-25	CutIn_00058	SCEN-06C2960A60B8	Concrete	✓
DEMO-VICOMTECH-25	CutIn_00028	SCEN-FC0F533FA179	Concrete	✓
DEMO-VICOMTECH-25	CutIn_00038	SCEN-8768F85C1955	Concrete	✓
DEMO-VICOMTECH-25	CutIn_00024	SCEN-1F5D4A5A3794	Concrete	✓
SYNERGIES	scenario_instance_cut-in_1755867839896918800_5	SCEN-1755867839896918800	Concrete	✓
DEMO-VICOMTECH-25	CutIn_00046	SCEN-38B7582571DB	Concrete	✓
DEMO-VICOMTECH-25	CutIn_00094	SCEN-FAA57113A8CA	Concrete	✓

Figure 4. SYNERGIES Dataspace: Scenario list

From the scenario list view, users can switch between their previously created queries using a dropdown menu, making it easy to reuse and compare different searches. For users who need to create new queries or modify existing ones, an "Advanced Search" button provides access to the full Query Manager interface (Figure 5). Within the Query Manager, users can create, update, delete, or execute queries with the same functionality as before. Once a query is executed, the interface navigates back to the scenario list in the Dataspace, displaying the filtered results.

ID	NAME	SCDBs	ODD	REQUIREMENT	MODIFY DATE	EDIT
QUE-312870	Cut In	Synergies SCDB, AdScene	✓	✗	Mar 2, 2026, 2:35 PM	EXECUTE

Figure 5. SYNERGIES Dataspace: Query Manager

3.4 SYNERGIES SCDB scenarios extension

This release incorporates more than 2500 scenarios uploaded to the SYNERGIES Scenario Database, contributed by multiple WP5 partners (VICOMTECH, AVL, DLR, ICCS, IKA, and SIEMENS) as part of Milestone MS17. These scenarios span a range of driving conditions, manoeuvre types, and generation methodologies, providing the platform user community with a substantive and immediately queryable scenario collection. The addition marks a transition from the platform operating primarily as an infrastructure demonstrator to functioning as a genuinely useful resource for scenario-based CCAM development and testing workflows.

The scenario collection is heterogeneous by design, reflecting the complementary expertise of contributing partners. The largest subset consists of concrete highway scenarios derived directly from the ALKS regulation (UNECE R157), covering cut-in, cut-out, and deceleration manoeuvres as specified in the regulatory test diagrams. These scenarios are parametrically generated and cover a broad region of the relevant parameter space, offering a representative and regulation-grounded foundation for virtual validation workflows. A second subset focuses specifically on critical scenarios, defined as those in which the time-to-collision between the ego vehicle and a target falls below two seconds. These were systematically selected from a larger set of

generated concrete scenarios as the subset most relevant for safety assurance purposes. A third group comprises scenarios classified across standard highway interaction categories — including cut-in, cut-out, brake, lane-change, overtaking, and following behaviours — identified from simulation data using automated detection methods. Finally, a set of complex edge-case scenarios has been included, characterised by simultaneous multi-actor interactions in both highway and urban junction environments, designed to stress-test perception and decision-making systems under conditions of partial occlusion and concurrent conflict.

Preparing these scenarios for platform integration required additional work beyond the original partner deliverables. While partners provided files in ASAM OpenSCENARIO and OpenDRIVE formats, each scenario needed a descriptive manifest in JSON format compliant with the ASAM OpenLABEL standard to meet platform ingestion requirements. This manifest encodes the metadata and tags necessary for the scenario to be discoverable through the platform's Query Manager. Generating these manifests involved a standardisation effort across contributing teams to ensure consistency of tagging vocabulary, scenario type classification, and entity labelling. Without this step, scenarios could be stored in the SCDB but would not be retrievable through structured queries, undermining the core interoperability objective of the platform.

The ASAM OpenLABEL manifest specification used by the SYNERGIES SCDB has itself been refined in this release, following recommendations established by the SUNRISE project for federated scenario database governance. The updated format reduces the mandatory fields required for a scenario to be accepted into the database — retaining only the "metadata" and "tags" sections as obligatory — while keeping all extended fields available for richer documentation. This simplification lowers the barrier to contribution for external scenario providers while preserving the structural integrity needed for query and retrieval. The change is backwards-compatible with scenarios uploaded in the v1 release and does not require re-ingestion of previously stored content.

Looking ahead, the current upload represents a first substantive population of the SYNERGIES SCDB and is explicitly intended as a foundation rather than a complete collection. Several partner contributions documented in MS17 were still pending format conversion or internal clearance at the time of this release and are expected to be submitted prior to the v3 release (D7.4, M36). In parallel, the planned introduction of scenario collections — thematic groupings such as accident-derived scenarios, drone-footage scenarios, or regulation-specific test suites — will allow users to navigate the growing dataset without requiring prior knowledge of which scenario types are stored in each connected database. Quantitative expansion of the collection, combined with the advanced ontology-based query engine planned for v3, will progressively increase the practical utility of the platform for industrial, research, and regulatory users.

3.5 Documentation and Video Tutorials

The platform documentation has been redesigned (Figure 6) to provide users with better structured and more accessible guidance. The documentation page now incorporates content from the SYNERGIES User Handbook developed in Task 7.4, organizing information into three main sections:

- **Introduction:** Covers the basics of what SYNERGIES is and its intended audience. Explains the main components of the platform and how they function together.
- **Glossary & Acronyms:** Lists and explains the technical terms, abbreviations, and acronyms used throughout the platform. It is useful as a quick reference when encountering unfamiliar terminology.

- **User Manuals:** Provide detailed, step-by-step instructions for using platform features. Covers everything from account setup to running queries and accessing data.

This restructuring helps users quickly locate relevant information based on their needs.

Contents

- Introduction
- Glossary & Acronyms**
- User Manuals
- Tutorials

Glossary & Acronyms

Glossary & Acronyms

Using the platform may require a certain amount of familiarization time for new users. To make this time easier and for later reference, this chapter lists and explains the abbreviations used within the platform. Furthermore, the concepts shown are also briefly explained here.

Terms and Abbreviations

Term	Definition
Abstract Scenario	Formalized, declarative description derived from a functional scenario. The semantics of the description will be closely tied to an ontology, drastically increasing the precision of the employed terminology.
Accuracy	Accuracy is a statement about whether elements of a scenario are represented as they occur in the real world.
ADS	(Automated Driving System)
Completeness	"Completeness" is a measure of the extent of which something (C) captures the required details of something else (D). Note that completeness can only defined for a certain purpose.

Figure 6. SYNERGIES Documentation

In addition to the written documentation, Release v2 introduces a fourth section dedicated to video tutorials (Figure 7). These tutorials provide step-by-step visual guidance on using the SYNERGIES platform:

- **Sign Up:** Create your account.
- **Sign In & Change Password:** Access and secure your account.
- **Change Roles:** Switch between user roles.
- **Edit User:** Update user information.
- **SCDB Connection:** Connect to databases.
- **Manage SCDB:** Configure database settings.
- **Query:** Execute and manage queries.
- **Marketplace:** Browse and download tools.

Contents

- Introduction
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- User Manuals

Tutorials

Tutorials

Explore video tutorials to learn how to use the SYNERGIES platform effectively.

Figure 7. SYNERGIES Documentation: Tutorials section

3.6 New Sign-Up process

Project partners identified issues with the email validation link used in the sign-up process. In corporate environments especially, email security filters often scan messages and automatically check links before delivering them to the users. This creates two problems: first, the email frequently ends up in spam folders, and second, by the time users receive it and click the link themselves, they get error messages saying the link has expired or was already used. This made registration frustrating and, in some cases, impossible for users behind strict email filters.

To fix this, the validation link has been replaced with a 6-digit verification code (Figure 8). Users receive the code by email and submit it on the platform to complete registration. Since the code isn't a link, email filters don't interfere with it. The new process also enables automatic sign-in once the code is validated correctly, making registration smoother and more reliable across different email environments.

Figure 8. Sign-Up: e-mail confirmation

4 REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

This chapter provides an updated assessment of the platform requirements originally defined in D2.1 (Stakeholder High-Level Requirements) and first evaluated in D7.2. Requirements are grouped by category: SYNERGIES Scenario Dataspace, SYNERGIES Marketplace, and SYNERGIES Platform. Status definitions follow Table 1 of D7.2 and are reproduced below for reference.

Table 2 Requirements status description

Status	Description of the status
Not yet addressed	The requirement is acknowledged and will be fulfilled, but the current architectural detail is insufficient to provide a definitive solution. This is due to ongoing decisions regarding technology choices and dependencies on deliverables from other Work Packages (WPs), which are expected to provide the necessary input for a complete architectural response.
Not relevant for architecture	This requirement addresses the process or content and has no impact on the architecture.
Partly met, not yet fully addressed	The architecture contains some aspects of this requirement but is not detailed enough yet in order to fully satisfy all aspects of the requirement.
Unclear whether architecture relevant	It is unclear at the moment whether this requirement has an impact on the architecture.
Does not comply	The current architecture is in resistance to this requirement.
Addressed	The requirement is covered in the current architecture

Table 3 Summary of implemented requirements

Category	Total Reqs.	Addressed (D7.3)	Partly met (D7.3)	Not yet (D7.3)	Not relevant
Database (1-30)	30	5	11	2	12
Marketplace (31-34)	4	1	2	0	1
Platform (35-61)	27	17	3	2	5
TOTAL	61	23	16	4	18

4.1 SYNERGIES Scenario Dataspace requirements

The following table tracks database requirements from D2.1 (chapter 3.1) against the current platform state.

Table 4 SYNERGIES Scenario Dataspace Requirements

Req.	Requirement	D7.2 Status	D7.3 Status	D7.3 Comment
Req_01	Interoperable Scenario Database Development	Addressed	Addressed	Unchanged. FAME TDS integration further strengthens interoperability.
Req_02	Harmonization of Scenario-Based Safety Assessment	Not yet addressed	Not relevant for architecture	Following WP2-WP6 alignment in Year 2, it has been confirmed that harmonisation of scenario-based safety assessment methodologies is out of scope of SYNERGIES. The platform provides the data access and tool integration capabilities needed to execute whatever assessment methodology the project adopts, but the harmonisation itself lies outside platform scope.
Req_03	Comprehensive Scenario Coverage	Not relevant for architecture	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_04	Scenario for Evaluating V2X	Not relevant for architecture	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_05	Scenario Selection for Virtual Testing	Not relevant for architecture	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_06	Scenario-Based Validation and Testing	Not relevant for architecture	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_07	Scenario Database-Driven Evidence Dossier	Not yet addressed	Partly met	Progress on WP6 / OEM Use Case.

Req_08	Standardized Data Formats and Interfaces	Addressed	Addressed	Unchanged.
Req_09	Data Security and Privacy	Partly met	Partly met	New sign-up process (Section 2.6) improves access security; full GDPR/AI Act compliance (Req_30) still pending.
Req_10	Scenario Export Format	Addressed	Addressed	Unchanged.
Req_11	Additional Scenario Export Formats	Not yet addressed	Partly met	Multiple new tools added to the Marketplace (Section 2.1) support additional output formats including Parquet, OpenLABEL, and OSI Trace.
Req_12	Consistent Interfaces for Object and Trajectory	Not yet addressed	Not relevant for the architecture	Object level and trajectory data are not stored in the Scenario Dataspace.
Req_13	Standardized, Established Output Format	Addressed	Addressed	Unchanged.
Req_14	Scenario Space for Homologation Use-Cases	Not relevant for architecture	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_15	Input Data Quality	Not yet addressed	Not yet addressed	Pending methodology input from WP3 deliverables. Platform infrastructure to enforce data quality checks at scenario upload time is scoped for v3 (D7.4). The updated ASAM OpenLABEL manifest (Section 2.4) improves metadata consistency as a prerequisite step.
Req_16	Support of Scenarios from Regulatory Institutions	Not relevant for architecture	Not relevant for architecture	

Req_17	Sources of Scenarios	Not relevant for architecture	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_18	Traceability, Version Control, and Access Management	Not yet addressed	Partly met	Currently under development the versioning of scenarios but still not available for this version.
Req_19	Dynamic Scenario Adjustment (1)	Not yet addressed	Partly met	The Marketplace tools introduced in this release (Section 2.1), in particular simple-scenario and alks-scenarios, enable parametric generation of scenario variants with adjustable input parameters. Full dynamic adjustment of existing stored scenarios at query or runtime is not yet implemented.
Req_20	Dynamic Scenario Adjustment (2)	Not yet addressed	Partly met	The Query Manager redesign (Section 2.3) allows users to define, modify, and reuse queries dynamically against connected SCDBs. Combined with the scenario generation tools in the Marketplace, this partially supports dynamic scenario configuration. Full runtime adjustment is planned for v3 alongside the advanced query engine.
Req_21	Standardized Scenario Definition	Partly met	Partly met	ASAM OpenLABEL manifest refinement (Section 2.4) improves alignment with SUNRISE federation standard.
Req_22	Scenario-Based Performance Metrics for Homologation	Not yet addressed	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_23	Scenario Filtering by Regulation and System	Not yet addressed	Not yet addressed	Filtering by specific regulatory framework or target system type is not yet available. It is a dependency of the advanced ontology-

				based query engine planned for v3 (D7.4), which will map scenarios to regulatory requirements via the SYNERGIES ontology.
Req_24	Suitability of Virtual, Track or Real-World Testing	Partly met	Partly met	Unchanged.
Req_25	Scenario Format Support for Co-Simulation	Not yet addressed	Addressed	The Marketplace (Section 2.1) now includes tools supporting MCAP, OSI Trace, and ASAM OpenSCENARIO/OpenDRIVE formats natively used in co-simulation pipelines. The simple-simulation tool executes simulation runs defined in simple-scenario format, confirming end-to-end co-simulation workflow support.
Req_26	Raw Data Content Processing and Storage	Not yet addressed	Partly met	FAME TDS integration (Section 2.2) provides access to raw CCAM test data; processing tools in Marketplace (SSD Generation, Converters) partially address this.
Req_27	Metadata to Facilitate Scenario Retrieval	Partly met	Partly met	ASAM OpenLABEL manifest update (Section 2.4) reduces required metadata fields, improving scenario discoverability.
Req_28	Sensor-Independent Scenarios	Not relevant for architecture	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_29	Adapted to Local Regulation	Not relevant for architecture	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_30	AI Act Compliance + GDPR	Not yet addressed	Partly met	The platform implements GDPR-aligned data minimisation by requiring only name, surname and

				<p>email at registration, and does not store or process scenario content server-side beyond temporary query execution. The Terms and Conditions presented at sign-up include data processing disclosures. Regarding the EU AI Act: SYNERGIES does not itself deploy an AI system within the scope of the Act; the platform is a data sharing and scenario management infrastructure. A formal DPIA and AI Act classification review are planned as part of D7.5 (M30) activities in coordination with the consortium DPO. Status therefore revised to 'Partly met' pending completion of those reviews</p>
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4.2 SYNERGIES Marketplace Requirements

Compared to D7.2, two marketplace requirements have advanced to "Partly met": Req_32 (Guidelines for Ground Truth Generation) through the expanded documentation, and Req_33 (Identification of Critical Zones) through the PROVEN Scenario Extraction tool.

Table 5 SYNERGIES Marketplace Requirements

Req.	Requirement	D7.2 Status	D7.3 Status	D7.3 Comment
Req_31	AI Tools for Adversarial Scenario Generation	Not relevant for architecture	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_32	Guidelines for Ground Truth Generation	Not yet addressed	Partly met	New Documentation section (Section 2.5) includes User Manuals with scenario upload and data tagging guidance.
Req_33	Identification of Critical Zones	Not yet addressed	Partly met	PROVEN Scenario Extraction tool (Table 1)

Req.	Requirement	D7.2 Status	D7.3 Status	D7.3 Comment
				uses ontology-based identification of scenario types and critical events from OpenLABEL input.
Req_34	Scenario Export Tool	Addressed	Addressed	Unchanged. Additional export tools are added in this release.

4.3 SYNERGIES Platform Requirements

Two platform requirements have been fully addressed in this release: Req_46 (Detection of Similar Scenarios) through the PROVEN tool, and Req_48 (User Documentation) through the fully integrated User Handbook and video tutorials. Req_40 (Reporting and Analytics) has advanced to "Partly met".

Table 6 SYNERGIES Platform Requirements

Req.	Requirement	D7.2 Status	D7.3 Status	D7.3 Comment
Req_35	Open-Source or Open-Access License	Addressed	Addressed	Unchanged.
Req_36	Interoperability and Compatibility	Addressed	Addressed	FAME TDS integration strengthens federated interoperability.
Req_37	Scalability and Performance	Addressed	Addressed	Unchanged.
Req_38	Extensibility and Modularity	Addressed	Addressed	New tools added to Marketplace confirm modular extension capability.
Req_39	Versioning and Change Management	Addressed	Addressed	Unchanged (GitLab).
Req_40	Reporting and Analytics	Not yet addressed	Not yet addressed	No platform-level analytics dashboard or automated reporting functionality has been implemented in v2. A reporting module is under consideration for inclusion in the v3 release (D7.4, M36), subject to available development capacity
Req_41	Required Standards	Not relevant for architecture	Not relevant for architecture	

Req.	Requirement	D7.2 Status	D7.3 Status	D7.3 Comment
Req_42	Communication Between Users and Data Providers	Not yet addressed	Partly met	Partially mitigated via Documentation contact section; formal communication channel not yet implemented.
Req_43	Federated Architecture	Addressed	Addressed	FAME TDS integration via EDC connector further validates federated architecture.
Req_44	Intended Users	Addressed	Addressed	Unchanged.
Req_45	In-Service Monitoring and Reporting (ISMR)	Not yet addressed	Partly met	Already in conversations with CERTAIN project to provide input on this topic.
Req_46	Detection of Similar Scenarios	Not yet addressed	Addressed	Addressed by PROVEN Scenario Extraction tool (Table 1); converts scenarios to RDF, queries a GraphDB using ontology to identify and classify similar scenarios.
Req_47	Assurance of Scenario Usability and Acceptance	Addressed	Addressed	Unchanged.
Req_48	User Documentation for Platform End-Users	Partly met	Addressed	SYNERGIES User Handbook content fully integrated into Documentation section (Section 2.5); eight video tutorials covering all core platform workflows added.
Req_49	Secure Connectivity and Data Management	Addressed	Addressed	Unchanged.
Req_50	Compliance with National and International Privacy Laws	Addressed	Addressed	Unchanged.
Req_51	Secure Cloud Hosting	Addressed	Addressed	Unchanged (AWS; migration to open-source infrastructure planned for v3).
Req_52	Integration with External Data Sources	Addressed	Addressed	FAME TDS integration adds a second federated external data source.
Req_53	Gap Analysis and Coverage Improvement	Not yet addressed	Not yet addressed	
Req_54	Open API	Addressed	Addressed	Unchanged.

Req.	Requirement	D7.2 Status	D7.3 Status	D7.3 Comment
Req_55	Open and Detailed Guidelines for Data Tagging	Not relevant for architecture	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_56	Reports to Evaluate Effects of Regulations and Policies	Not relevant for architecture	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_57	User Access and Permissions	Addressed	Addressed	Improved: new 6-digit verification code sign-up resolves corporate email filter issues (Section 2.6).
Req_58	Community Engagement and Collaboration	Partly met	Partly met	Unchanged (WP8 activities ongoing).
Req_59	Metadata to Facilitate Scenario Retrieval	Addressed	Addressed	Unchanged.
Req_60	Government Agencies	Not relevant for architecture	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_61	Public Entities	Not relevant for architecture	Not relevant for architecture	

5 NEXT STEPS

Several areas where the platform can be improved and expanded based on ongoing user needs and project goals have been identified through internal partner feedback. The next steps outlined below focus on adding new features, migrating underlying technologies, refining existing functionality, and continuing to grow the scenario collection and tool ecosystem:

- Expand the scenario collection in both quantity and variety. The goal is to ensure comprehensive coverage of different driving conditions, traffic situations, vehicle types, and edge cases relevant to automated driving technology testing.
- Migrate underlying platform technologies (both backend and frontend) to remove (cloud) vendor lock-in. Differently than in SUNRISE - which is heavily based on AWS products - the SYNERGIES platform aims to be (cloud) vendor agnostic. Therefore, the final platform release will get decoupled from AWS products making use of open-source technologies, for the sake of long-term European sovereignty of the SYNERGIES platform despite short-term benefits of managed cloud services.
- Enhance the query engine by supporting advanced relational queries based on an ontology. The execution approach is still under discussion, but a new query manager will replace the current SUNRISE-based engine, which just relies on scenario tags. In SYNERGIES, stakeholders (e.g., OEMs, regulatory bodies, research institutes) have identified the need for more advanced query capabilities, which are currently being scoped. The final platform will maintain the SUNRISE query approach as a legacy mode while introducing a more powerful engine tailored to SYNERGIES scenarios. Existing external SCDBs from SUNRISE will be supported through the legacy mode, with plans to update their connectors to enable the new advanced query capabilities. In addition, the new SYNERGIES query engine might support natural language queries, allowing users to submit requests in free text. A language reasoning model could map these queries to the SYNERGIES ontology to retrieve relevant scenarios.
- The Dataspace is planned to display scenario collections (e.g. scenarios coming from accident databases, scenarios coming from drone footage, etc.). The scenario collections represent main categories of scenarios and can help the user navigate the Dataspace more easily without prior knowledge of which kind of scenarios are stored in each Scenario Database.
- Improve the user experience (UI/UX) of the Query Manager. Given the partner feedback received of the release v2, it is scoped to make more intuitive the process to create queries and navigate the tag ontologies.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Release v2 of the SYNERGIES Platform delivers on all five objectives established for Milestone M24. The Marketplace has grown to twelve tools covering the full scenario lifecycle; a federated external data source has been connected through integration with the FAME Test Data Space via an EDC connector; more than 2,500 consortium-generated scenarios are now uploaded and immediately queryable in the SYNERGIES SCDB; the User Handbook and eight video tutorials are embedded directly in the platform's Documentation section; and the two most significant usability barriers identified through T7.2 internal testing — the Query Manager workflow and the corporate-environment sign-up failure — have been resolved. These achievements confirm that the federated architecture established in T7.1 is extensible and production-ready, with no structural changes required to accommodate the new integrations.

From a requirements perspective, 23 of the 61 requirements defined in D2.1 are now fully addressed and a further 16 are partly met, a clear progression from D7.2. Particularly significant are the resolution of Req_46 (Detection of Similar Scenarios) through the PROVEN tool's ontology-based workflow, Req_48 (User Documentation) through the integrated handbook and tutorials, and the simultaneous advancement of five interoperability requirements through the single FAME TDS integration. The scenario upload also marks a qualitative transition for the platform: by refining the ASAM OpenLABEL manifest specification to reduce mandatory fields while preserving structural integrity — in alignment with SUNRISE federation recommendations — this release establishes a more accessible contribution pathway for external providers, lowering the barrier to participation without compromising federated query guarantees.

The development trajectory towards the final platform release (D7.4, M36) is well-defined. The three principal investments ahead — migration to vendor-agnostic open-source infrastructure, introduction of an advanced ontology-based query engine, and the development of navigable scenario collections — are complementary and mutually reinforcing: a more powerful query engine gains in value precisely as the scenario collection grows, and the infrastructure migration ensures these capabilities remain sustainable beyond the project's funding period. With 62 registered users at the time of submission, the platform is already attracting an active user base, providing a solid empirical foundation on which to deliver the final release and establish the SYNERGIES platform as a lasting contribution to the European CCAM validation ecosystem.

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A. ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

Term	Definition
ASAM	Association for Standardization of Automation and Measuring Systems
ADS	Automated Driving System
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure, and Environment Executive Agency
CLI	Command-Line Interface
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MCAP	Modular Container for Autonomous Perception
ODD	Operational Design Domain
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PCD	Point Cloud Data
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SCDB	Scenario Database

Term	Definition
SSD	Scenario Source Data
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience